

ORGANIZING THE ACTIVITY OF MANAGERS IN THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

Nuridinov Ulugbek Shikirlaevich

Chief accountant of Namangan specialized culture school
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Annotation: This article provides full information about the management system, the role of the management apparatus in organizing the activities of managers, and optimizing the work of the management apparatus.

Keywords: Manager, management work, management system, Japanese method, American method, attestation in evaluating managers, rating system, standardization of documents, control.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada menejment tizimi, menejerlar faoliyatini tashkil etishda boshqaruv apparatining o'рни, boshqaruv apparati mehnatini maqbullashtirish haqida to'liq ma'lumot berilgan.

Tayanch iboralar: Menejer, menejment mehnati, menejment tizimi, yapon usuli, amerika usuli, menejerlarni baholashda attestatsiya, reyting tizimi, hujjatlarni standartlash, nazorat.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена полная информация о системе управления, роли аппарата управления в организации деятельности менеджеров, оптимизации работы аппарата управления.

Ключевые слова: Менеджер, управленческая работа, система управления, японский метод, американский метод, аттестация при оценке менеджеров, рейтинговая система, стандартизация документов, контроль.

When organizing the work of a manager, it is necessary to ensure that the work of each executive in the management apparatus is limited and relatively uniform. This makes it possible to increase labor productivity, improve the quality of work, and increase the experience of each performer. Specialization should define the scope of responsibilities in such a way that each employee's issue is fully utilized as much as possible. Labor cooperation envisages the establishment of communication between management organizations and employees of various divisions of the management apparatus. In the management process, the activities of individual employees, services and departments outside of this enterprise are combined. The ways of division of labor and cooperation of managers are determined by the regulations on structural units and job instructions of management staff. On the basis of the Law "On Enterprises", job instructions are developed for each manager, specialist and technical executive in the enterprise and its divisions. Position

instructions, rights and obligations are determined on the basis of the principle of sole leadership. Position instructions and rules should be periodically restructured, corrected and supplemented, taking into account the improvement of production, labor and management processes.

Optimizing the work of the management apparatus In order to ensure a unified approach to the optimization of the work of the management apparatus, a definition-qualification reference is also used, which includes the complexity of the work to be performed by employees, the leadership position, the level required for those who perform various management tasks, and seniority is shown most of the working time (77%) is spent working with documents in management technology. Therefore, it is necessary to constantly improve the exchange of documents. The manager's work is also greatly influenced by the direction of information flows and the acceptability of document circulation technology in the enterprise and organization. Here, reducing the number of stages through which documents go through as a result of combining them has a great effect, and as a result, unjustified coordination is eliminated. If coordination is important, swapping the steps in the document transition works well. In order to reduce the time spent on the exchange of documents, transition technology and optimal ways of information transmission are determined. The leader only signs documents that cannot be handed over to others. The use of special sample texts and standard sheets is of great importance in saving work time related to the preparation of letters.

In correspondence between enterprises and organizations, it is widely used to return the received document with an answer. Unification and standardization of documents is an important direction of organizing the manager's work. The use of standard sheets leads to fewer errors and, as a result, lower administrative costs. The mechanization and automation of the manager's work is especially important in the conditions where the volume of information is constantly increasing. According to experts, it is possible to mechanize 70% of the work in the management apparatus with the help of organizational and computing machines, communication tools.[1]

An important direction of improving the manager's work is the optimal organization of the workplace and, first of all, the placement of work characteristics, the interaction of departments, taking into account the importance of work. Desks, equipment, shelves, filing cabinets should be placed conveniently and within reach. Requirements for continuous operation should be taken into account when placing workplaces and equipping them with

technical tools and auxiliary equipment. It is known from experience that placing the workplace in accordance with the requirements of 100 technologies, ergonomics, psychophysiology, aesthetics allows to increase labor productivity (by 5% or more). It is important to create conditions for the work of the control apparatus, taking into account sanitary and hygienic standards, temperature, humidity, light standards, noise level, as well as work and rest procedures. Labor productivity Labor productivity is greatly influenced by the psychological factor, the employees and the manager, as well as the mutual relations between the employees. Their mood, work activity, work results depend on this factor. The effectiveness of management is mainly related to how successfully the leader performs his task. The manager of the current era should introduce new scientific and technical solutions and methods of labor and management organization, economically expand production possibilities. A manager should have the qualities of an organizer, an educator, a seeker, and an administrator. The complexity of the decisions made by the managers and the increase in responsibility, the variety of the work to be performed, require them to allocate their time efficiently.[2]

Managers who do not know how to plan their activities and deal only with current issues have time to analyze the results of one or another situation arising in the management process, and do not have time to decide what needs to be done in the future. When determining the goal of the manager's activity, first of all, it is necessary to proceed from the tasks facing the higher management system, otherwise, it is possible to act inconsistently (or contrary) to the activity of the whole system. The speed of the leader's work, his work requires complete rest, as well as changing the types of work during the working day, because only in this way can the work be highly effective and the ability to work can be fully restored. In the work of a manager, it is very important to establish an acceptable work pattern, a constant order of actions performed by him. Most of the manager's working time is spent working with documents. The amount of received information (letter, order, document, etc.) is very large. In this case, it is very important to "filter" the information. The leader should be given information that only he can handle. At this stage, the leader is greatly assisted by a secretary or assistant (referent) who distributes information among the executives. He should be a qualified employee, he should know the characteristics of the activities of all departments and organizations of management. Optimal distribution of responsibilities between the leader and the management apparatus subordinate to him allows the leader to spend his

working time efficiently. Executors should be allowed to sign as many documents as possible within existing legislation. This allows to save the manager's time, increase the initiative and responsibility of the performers. Various meetings and meetings occupy an important place in the activities of managers, and 77% of their working time is spent on them.[3] Therefore, in order to properly organize the meetings, it is necessary to pay special attention to the following: - the issue discussed at the meeting should consist only of the problem to be solved by the team. This problem should be solved during one session; - participants of the meeting should have sufficient experience and knowledge on the discussed problem; - the topic of the issues discussed at the meeting should be announced to the participants in advance so that they have time to prepare; - the date, time and place of the meeting should be indicated in advance, because its participants should plan their working hours. The leader of the meeting should determine the purpose and form of the meeting in advance. It is also important to conduct the meeting and create conditions for a free, productive discussion. Among the many responsibilities of the leader, it is necessary to single out receiving visitors and conducting interviews. It is important to set aside time for employee-initiated reception, because an "open door policy" that looks democratic from the outside can lead to a waste of working time.[4]

During the interview, the leader should try to find out their intentions from the employees by asking questions, justify their requests or suggestions. If the conversation starts at the initiative of the manager, the employee should have a clear name about the time and purpose of the conversation. This allows the employee to prepare for the content of the issue and avoid psychological stress. Creating an atmosphere of mutual trust during the conversation will give it a chance to be successful. In this case, the manager should take into account the purpose of the interview and the employee's characteristics. At the end of the conversation, the leader must make a note of the result achieved on the discussed issue and ways to solve it later. One of the important factors of the effectiveness of the leader's work is the organization of control over the implementation of the decisions made. Control is a permanent task of the manager, which should be taken into account in his work plan and is carried out by familiarization with materials, reception for personal information, and inspection. A convenient form of control is to record tasks using special term cards and punch cards. [5]

The leader must create conditions for the smooth operation of the entire team and management apparatus, because the entire management system and, as a result, the entire production efficiency depends on this. Summary Managerial work is an integral part of the work of product manufacturers. Elements of the production process, management relations, information, various documents, and management decisions are taken as the subject of the manager's work. A modern manager needs high economic thinking, professional skills, foresight, knowledge of sociology and psychology. The enterprise should always take care of the manager's professional skills and morale.

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